

IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE BIOLOGICAL STUDENTS IS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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ANNOTATION: This article highlights the scientific and theoretical foundations and methodological features of improving the professional and methodological competence of future biology teachers.

KEYWORDS: educational effectiveness, professional and methodological competence, interactive method, cognitive activity, qualification requirements, integration, self-control.

In the context of reforms being implemented on a global scale, one of the current strategic directions is recognized as the training of competitive, mature personnel in accordance with international standards, as well as the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation through a fundamental reform of the content and quality of education. It is noted that attention to education at all stages of the continuous education system is the foundation for the development of the economies of all developed countries.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5847 of October 8, 2019, "On Approving the Concept of Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030," outlines tasks for raising the content of higher education to a qualitatively new level, establishing a system for training highly qualified personnel capable of making a worthy contribution to the sustainable development of the social sphere and economic sectors, finding their.

In the process of implementing these tasks, there arose a need for a fundamental reform of the content of education. This necessity, based on the demands of today, requires the content of education in Singapore, which has been a leader in the global education system for many years, achieving high ratings for students of general education schools, the creation of a new generation of textbooks based on it, unlike existing textbooks, that is, localization work is being carried out intensively, and as a result, it requires knowledge, skills, qualifications, and competence from future subject teachers who are entering pedagogical activity at the threshold of primary school in accordance with international standards. Furthermore, the regular and systematic improvement of the professional and methodological competence of personnel working in the continuous education system in accordance with the demands of today's conditions of digital education transformation and the labor market is one of the pressing pedagogical problems[1].

In the process of rapid development of science and technology, competitiveness requires each specialist to possess professional and methodological competence and consistently improve it. The issues of improving the professional and methodological competence of future specialists are considered as an object of research in the activities of future teachers of science, that is, students, in higher educational institutions. In particular, the significance and tasks of general pedagogical (N. Azizkhodzhaeva), creative (V. Kan-Kalik), and innovative (V. Slastenin) training have been studied[5,31-37-b.].

Of course, the competency-based approach in the field of pedagogy is not a completely new phenomenon, many scientists, such as N.V. Kuzmina, A.K. Markova, E.F. Zeer, and V.A. Slastenin, have done a lot of work on the professional competence of a teacher[9].

In her research, B. Nazarova notes that in the philosophy of D. Dewey, W. Waller, M. Mead, K. Jung, and F. Znanetsky, the concept of professional competence is defined as follows: "It is a means of learning in the environment, a means of learning." [5; 13-c.].

According to N.V. Kuzmina, competence is characterized by qualities and abilities that help solve various situations and problems that arise in life. Professional competence is adherence to the standard that exists in a particular profession [2].

According to R.Kh. Tugeshev, professional mastery is a competency acquired only for one activity through steps taken towards improving personal qualities. The owner of competence is not limited to the mastery and mastery of his work, but also implies qualities such as the organization of work, a systematic

understanding of all problems related to his work, the ability to set goals and find solutions to specific problems [7; 14-c.].

E.F. Zeer advances the idea that professionally oriented competence and professional abilities ensure a high level of professional mastery. Professional competence is considered one of the four aspects of an individual's subjective activity and represents a combination of knowledge, skills, and methods of carrying out professional activities related to one's profession[3].

Numerous scientific studies are being conducted in educational and research institutions of our country to enhance the professional and methodological competence of future biology teachers. However, scientists' interest in various aspects of this problem is increasingly growing day by day. This circumstance attests to its particular significance and relevance in the context of globalization in the educational process.

Our research has shown that, based on a comparative analysis of pedagogical, psychological, and methodological literature, it is necessary to directly familiarize oneself with the content of theoretical sources, as well as with educational and regulatory documents for higher education institutions and general secondary schools. However, the interest of scientists in various aspects of this problem and its aspects is increasing day by day. This circumstance testifies to its special significance and relevance in the context of globalization in the educational process.

Our research has shown that, based on a comparative analysis of pedagogical, psychological, and methodological literature, it is necessary to directly familiarize oneself with the content of theoretical sources, as well as with educational and regulatory documents for higher and secondary schools:

- between the level of mature specialist education for students and the regulatory requirements for the modernized content and scope of State Educational Standards and Curriculum, as well as their individual capabilities;
- between the pedagogical activities of higher education institutions and the mechanisms and established patterns for developing processes to prepare students for their future role as teachers;
- among the methods used in the process of improving the professional and methodological competence of future biology teachers in higher education institutions;
- the insufficient integration of mandatory and elective subjects in psychological and pedagogical disciplines during the development of creative competencies for future biology teachers;
- between the content of standard curricula in higher education institutions, the curricula of universities ranked among the world's Top-300, and the content and curriculum of general secondary education schools;
- It is advisable to highlight the contradictory and debatable aspects, such as the content of textbooks intended for students and the insufficient number of tasks within them that promote creative thinking in line with international research programs[1;5].

One of the ways to positively solve these contradictions is to train future biology teachers in "General psychology", "General pedagogy", "Biology teaching methodology", "Innovative technologies in teaching biology", "Biology Solving problems and exercises" and other compulsory and elective subjects, solving problems and exercises based on international requirements that serve to improve professional and methodological competence by introducing the module, it is desirable to apply it to all forms of teaching from tasks with different levels of complexity. At the same time, to improve the professional and methodical competence of students, to create psychological and pedagogical conditions necessary to ensure methodical and individual development in HEIs, to modernize the content and structure of the training of future biology teachers based on the requirements of the present time, determines the main goal of forming the creativity of the future specialist by developing self-control and assessment mechanisms in accordance with international experiences.

In the process of training the pedagogical personnel of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular, among the actual methodological tasks assigned to the future teachers of biology in the higher education system - the scientific and methodological knowledge and skill acquisition required for the specialist in the qualification requirements, the pedagogic profession to form and develop the love for children, to continuously improve their pedagogical skills within the framework of the 4+2 program, to be able to correctly design the methodical system of classes, to use innovative technologies and methods that allow to improve their professional-methodical competence should be able to choose and effectively apply it during his future pedagogical activity. The main goal of improving the professional and methodological competence of future biology teachers based on foreign experiences is to form the ideological immunity of the young generation that is forming in New Uzbekistan, work with loyalty to the Motherland, international research (PISA, PIRLIS, TIMSS, etc.) is to take a place among the countries with a high ranking as a

result of ensuring its appropriate participation. Of course, in order to improve the professional-methodical competence of students of higher education institutions, directing them to professional pedagogical activities, occupying a certain level of position, which at the same time is a process inextricably linked with the system of psychological, pedagogical, methodical and scientific approaches in professional relations[10; 203-b.].

In the conditions of today's digital transformation, the main pedagogical problem facing the higher education system is to prepare future specialists who are flexible to the rapidly changing educational environment based on the demands of the labor market in accordance with international standards, who can independently choose information, and process information in their pedagogical activities. training of skilled professionals who can effectively apply, evaluate themselves objectively, apply theoretically acquired knowledge and skills to their future practical life, and develop the competence of collaboration. Also, developing mechanisms for improving the training of future teachers based on scientific-theoretical, scientific-methodical, pedagogical-psychological requirements, enriching the content of qualification requirements and model science program based on the latest achievements of science, during his pedagogical activity effective use of innovative technologies, implementation of projects and modeling works based on creative criteria and principles are important pedagogical problems[4].

It was considered appropriate to develop the above-mentioned creative competencies in future teachers studying in higher education institutions in the following directions:

- the ability to correctly choose basic sciences that allow to improve the professional-methodical competence of the biology teacher of the first direction;
- ensuring the interaction of the second line of psychological and pedagogical sciences with compulsory and optional subjects included in the curriculum during the improvement of the professional and methodological competence of the future biology teacher;
- to increase the content of the textbooks intended for the students of the third direction and the share of assignments that serve creative thinking within the framework of international research programs;
- implementation of interactive methods in educational practice that allow improving professional-methodical competence of the fourth direction.

To sum up, the suggestions and recommendations made from the above scientific and theoretical point of view mean that it is a priority to improve the professional-methodical competence of the biology teacher. Therefore, every teacher should regularly improve his professional-methodical competence.

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